

Table continued

Variety	Origin	Relative root length ^a
Nang Coi	Vietnam	0.85
Bayar Kuning	Indonesia	0.85
Bjm-11	Indonesia	0.85
Thung Hoa Binh	Vietnam	0.85
Alabio	Indonesia	0.81
Khao Seetha	Thailand	0.81
Gaw Diaw Bow	Indonesia	0.80
Khao Taeng	Thailand	0.80
Lua Thuoc Co	Vietnam	0.79
Talang A	Indonesia	0.78
Mahakam	Indonesia	0.78
Galambong	Indonesia	0.77
Tai Nguyen	Vietnam	0.77
Ketambar	Indonesia	0.74
Thom Ran	Vietnam	0.74
Talang B	Indonesia	0.73
Duvi Trau	Vietnam	0.70
Can Dung Phen	Vietnam	0.70
Gogo Ranceh	Indonesia	0.70
Doc Phung	Vietnam	0.68
Nang Gao	Vietnam	0.67
Mansirit	Indonesia	0.67
Kapus	Indonesia	0.66
Yaca	West Africa	0.66
S-1	West Africa	0.66
Atanha	West Africa	0.62
Nang Co	Vietnam	0.62
Than Nang Do	Vietnam	0.62
Pokkali	India	0.62
Soc Nau	Vietnam	0.59
Silla	West Africa	0.57
S-4	West Africa	0.45
IRAT104 (tolerant check)		0.83
IR1552 (susceptible check)		0.57
CV (%)		12.5
LSD (0.05)		0.21
LSD (0.01)		0.28

^a Mean of two replications.

higher than that of IRAT104. Varieties Siyam, Lemo, Khao Daeng, Siyamhalus, Bjm-12, Ketan, Seribu Gantang, Bayar Raden Rati, and Padi Kanji also produced significantly higher RRLs than did IRAT104. The tolerance level of the other cultivars was comparable with that of IRAT104. Only three of the 62 varieties expressed sensitivity.

The results indicated that tolerance for Al toxicity exists in lowland varieties grown on acid sulfate soils. The cultivars that are more tolerant of Al than upland cultivar IRAT104 may be good donors for breeding Al-tolerant lowland rice varieties. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Karnataka Rice Hybrid-1, a short-duration hybrid for Karnataka, India

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Karnataka Rice Hybrid-1 (KRH-1) is a short-duration rice hybrid selected at RRS from rice hybrids shared by IRRI through the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. Its parents are cytoplasmic male sterile line IR58025 A and restorer line IR9761-19-1 R.

KRH-1 matures in 125 d and is 90-cm tall. It produces an average of 460 panicles/m² and 168 grains/panicle. The grains are long-slender and straw-colored, the kernels

are white, and the 1,000-grain weight is 23.3 g. It is for use in the irrigated areas of Karnataka. The recommended fertilizer dose for KRH-1 is 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. The seed rate is 20 kg/ha with single seedlings per hill at 20 × 10-cm spacing.

KRH-1 recorded a yield advantage of 1.5 t/ha over check Mangala in trials conducted during 1990-93 at Mandya (see table). Similar results were obtained in multilocation trials and in 100 on-farm trials around Karnataka, in which KRH-1 yielded an average 6.8 t/ha with a yield advantage of 1.5 t/ha over Mangala. KRH-1 has moderate resistance to neck blast, sheath rot, and stem borer.

The State Variety Release Committee released KRH-1 during 1994 for cultivation in Karnataka State. ■

Mean yield (t/ha) of Karnataka Rice Hybrid-1 (KRH-1) in different trials in Karnataka, India. 1990-93.

Type of trial	Year	Trials (no.)	KRH-1	Mangala (check)	Yield advantage
Research station (Mandya)	1990-93	10	7.2	5.7	1.5
Multilocation	1991-93	18	5.3	3.7	1.6
On-farm	1991-93	100	6.8	5.3	1.5
Demonstration	1993	10	6.3	5.0	1.3
Mean			6.4	4.9	1.5

Xiangyou 63, a quasi-aromatic hybrid rice with good quality and high yield

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Xiangyou 63 was developed at HHRRC using aromatic cytoplasmic male sterile line Xiangxiang 2 A and nonaromatic restorer line Minghui 63. It was released to farmers in Jan 1995. Xiangyou 63 is the first quasi-aromatic hybrid rice in China, and Xiangxiang 2A, developed from the cross V20A/N20 B/MR365 by HHRRC, is the first aromatic CMS line in China. The hybrid has so far been planted on more than 20,000 ha and seems popular with farmers and consumers. In addition to being aromatic, the hybrid has good grain quality, high-yielding ability, good disease resistance, and wide adaptability.

The hybrid, which produces only some aromatic grains on each plant, has some advantages over aromatic inbred or hybrid rices. In China, aromatic inbred and hybrid rices are usually mixed before cooking with nonaromatic rice to lessen their intense aroma. Xiangyou 63 grain, however, is already mixed due to F₂ segregation.

Another advantage is that its grains are not as easily attacked by insect pests and rats as are those of aromatic rices, and that it is also relatively easier to store than aromatic rice.

All of Xiangyou 63's quality characters, except brown rice percentage, meet the first and second class standards of fine quality rice issued by the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (Table 1). It has been endorsed as a fine quality rice in Hunan, Guangdong, Yunnan, Guizhou, Shaanxi, and Henan provinces.

Xiangyou 63 yielded an average of about 6.9 t/ha in various trials during 1987-89. For example, in the 1988-89 Hunan